

[microreview]

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Gödel's incompleteness theorem in a nutshell

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October 19, 2022

Abstract

We present a microversion of Gödel's incompleteness theorem.

keywords: Gödel's theorem, logic, axiomatic system

The most updated version of this white paper is available at

<https://osf.io/gphsk/download>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7225977>

Introduction

1. Gödel's theorem is a very complex theorem regarding truths that are not provable [1, 2].
2. Undecidable means not provable.
3. Let G be a set of undecidable theorems.
4. All mathematics we are aware of is within the Axiomatic System (AS).
5. *Whether G is inside or outside the AS is an open mathematical question* [3].

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The meaning of notation in Logics

6. A symbol composed of strings and parenthesis has a special meaning in logics.
7. We will provide one example in this section for pedagogical purpose.
8. Suppose that Y is a symbol, meaning the mathematical formula $y = x + 1$.
9. Let $\text{nat}(Y, x, 1)$ be the result of substituting $x = 1$ in Y .
10. Then, $\text{nat}(Y, x, 1) = 2$.
11. If we want to repeat the process (9) r times with $r \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$, we write $\text{nat}(Y, x, r) = r + 1$.
12. *So, we can define an algorithm by means of strings.*

Mapping

13. Gödel showed a way of mapping theorems into arithmetic.
14. By (13), we understand that arithmetic is modeling the AS, not the contrary.
15. (14) can be justified for the way Gödel's numbers are introduced, as we will see in the next section.

Gödel's numbering system

16. Gödel's numbering system is a way of *quantifying theorems in AS* in order to *do some arithmetics* with them, such as **self-recurrence**.
17. Let's consider the following mapping: for each mathematical symbol, it is assigned a natural number.

symbol	Gödel's number	meaning
\neg	1	not
\vee	2	or
\rightarrow	3	if then
\exists	4	exists at least one
$=$	5	equal
0	6	zero
s	7	immediate successor of
(8	punctuation mark
)	9	punctuation mark
.	10	punctuation mark
+	11	addition
\times	12	multiplication

18. For each mathematical formula, it will be assigned a unique Gödel number using primes.

19. For example, m is the Gödel number for $1 = 1$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &1 = 1 \\
 &s0 = s0 \\
 &\downarrow\downarrow\downarrow\downarrow\downarrow \\
 &76576 \\
 &2^7 \cdot 3^6 \cdot 5^5 \cdot 7^7 \cdot 11^6 \\
 &m = 425\,431\,762\,237\,666\,800\,000
 \end{aligned}$$

Gödel's theorem

20. **Theorem.** *There is a formula not provable within an axiomatic system.*

21. Proof
22. $g_i :=$ Gödel number for $i \in \mathbb{N}$
23. Each g_i is mapped into a single formula or theorem.
24. Suppose g_1 proves g_2 .
25. Let $\text{dem}(g_1, g_2)$ be the arithmetic relation between the integers g_1 and g_2 .
26. $\exists g_1 \text{dem}(g_1, g_2)$ means that there is a sequence of formulas (with Gödel number g_1) that proves a formula with Gödel number g_2 .
27. $\neg \exists g_1 \text{dem}(g_1, g_2)$ means that there is NO sequence of formulas (with Gödel number g_1) that proves a formula with Gödel number g_2 .
28. Suppose $\neg \exists g_i \text{dem}(g_i, g_{not})$.
29. g_{not} is undecidable (i.e., not provable).
30. Let $\neg \exists g_i \text{dem}(g_i, g_{not})$ have Gödel number g .
31. We write $g = \neg \exists g_i \text{dem}(g_i, g_{not})$.
32. Let $\text{sub}(g_j, 17, g_j)$ be the Gödel number for a formula g_j when we substitute the variable y (which has Gödel number 17) by the number g_j , for $j \neq i$.
33. Suppose, without loss of generality, $g_{not} = \text{sub}(g_j, 17, g_j)$, then

$$g = \neg \exists g_i \text{dem}(g_i, g_{not}) = \neg \exists g_i \text{dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g_j, 17, g_j)).$$
34. (33) means that the formula with Gödel number $\text{sub}(g_j, 17, g_j)$ is undecidable.
35. Let $g_j = g$.

36. From (31), (33), and (35),

$$\begin{aligned}g &= \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, g_{not}) \\ &= \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g_j, 17, g_j)) \\ &= \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g, 17, g)).\end{aligned}$$

37. So,

$$g = \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g, 17, g)).$$

38. In (37), g appears both at the left and right hand side.

39. Note that (37) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}g &= \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(\neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g, 17, g)), 17, \\ &\quad \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g, 17, g)))) = \dots\end{aligned}$$

40. Inserting $g_j = g$ in $g_{not} = \text{sub}(g_j, 17, g_j)$,

$$g_{not} = \text{sub}(g, 17, g).$$

41. (40) means that the proposition “this formula is NOT provable” is replaced in the y variable by “this formula is NOT provable.”

42. From (31), $g = \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, g_{not}) = \neg\exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g, 17, g))$.

43. If g is provable, then $\neg g = \exists g_i \text{ dem}(g_i, \text{sub}(g, 17, g))$ is true.

44. In other words, **g is provable if and only if g is not provable.**

45. Therefore, **g is undecidable.** □

Final Remarks

46. In summary, by inserting “**this formula is NOT provable**” into itself, one obtains g .

47. There is a similarity in the definition of an *axiom* and *undecidable theorems*.
48. *Axiom* is an unprovable statement because it is *self-evident*.
49. A Gödel's undecidable proposition is an unprovable statement which is **not obvious**.
50. So, the difference from (48) and (49) is that undecidability is not evident.
51. *One question still remains: Is undecidability inside or outside the axiomatic system [3]?*
52. *What happens if one applies Gödel's numbering system to the transfinite ordinals ω ?*

Open Invitation

Review, add content, and co-author this white paper [4, 5].

*Join the **Open Mathematics Collaboration**.*

Send your contribution to mplobo@uft.edu.br.

Supplementary files

The **latex file** for this *white paper* together with other *supplementary files* are available in [6, 7].

How to cite this paper?

<https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/gphsk>

<https://zenodo.org/record/7225977>

Acknowledgements

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